

Statement by the Independent International Commission on Decommissioning (IICD), 30 May 2001

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**STATEMENT BY THE
INDEPENDENT INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION ON DECOMMISSIONING
(IICD)
30 May 2001**

To: The Rt Hon. John Reid, MP Secretary of State for Northern Ireland, Belfast	To: Mr. John O'Donoghue, TD, Minister of Justice, Equality and Law Reform, Dublin
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1. We have been advised by the Inspectors that they have carried out a third inspection of IRA arms. A copy of their [report](#) is attached.

2. Since our reported meeting in March with the IRA representative, we have continued to engage with him in the pursuit of our mandate.

Signed: Tauno Nieminen John de Chastelain Andrew D. Sens

Belfast, 30 May 2001

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